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COMPARISON OF HYPOXIC INDUCIBLE FACTOR 1 ALPHA (HIF1 α) BETWEEN GASTRITIS POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE *HELICOBACTER PYLORI*

Risna Wati*¹, GontarAlamsyah Siregar² & Dharma Lindarto¹

¹Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sumatera Utara

²Gastroenterohepatology Division, Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sumatera Utara

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Abstract

Introduction: Gastritis is a conditions with inflammation of the lining of the stomach. *Helicobacter pylori* (*H.pylori*) is the main etiology of chronic gastritis. Hypoxic Inducible Factor (HIF) is a transcription factor involved in adaptation to low oxygen conditions. HIF also prolongs the life of neutrophils by inhibiting the apoptotic pathway. HIF has a role in inflammatory signals.

Aim: To determine the ratio of HIF1- α levels in gastritis patients with positive and negative *H.pylori* with blood samples from HIF1- α not from the gastric mucosa.

Methods: This study was cross sectional design was conducted on 80 people with gastritis, diagnosed histopathologically based on examination of tissue taken during a gastroscopy. *H. pylori* was examined by CLO method and HIF levels by ELISA sandwich method using Invitrogen HIF-1 Alpha Elisa Kit. Data analysis was performed using the Mann Whitney Test.

Result: Significant differences were found where HIF-1 α levels in positive *H. pylori* were higher than negative *H. pylori* (p <0.05).

Conclusion: There were significant differences between HIF-1 α levels in positive and negative *H.pylori*.

Introduction

Dyspepsia is a condition that is often found in daily clinical practice. It is estimated that 30% of cases in general practice and 50-60% in gastroenterological practices are cases of dyspepsia.^{1,2}Based on the results of study in Asian countries, 43-79.5% of patients with dyspepsia are functional dyspepsia. ²According to the Indonesian Health Profile Data in 2007, dyspepsia ranked the tenth most inpatients in hospitals in 2006 with 34.029 patients, or around 1.59% of total care.^{1,3}

The pathogenesis of functional dyspepsia is caused by heterogeneous and multifactorial factors, such as gastroduodenal motility disorders, sensorimotor dysfunction associated with hypersensitivity to mechanical and chemical stimuli, immune activity, increased mucosal permeability in the proximal small intestine, disorders of the autonomic and enteric nervous system, *H. pylori*, and psychological conditions.^{2,4}

Persistent colonization of *H. pylori* in the gastric mucosa can develop into various pathological forms, such as peptic ulcer.⁷The prevalence of *H. pylori* in functional dyspepsia patients varies from 39% to 87%. The association of *H. pylori* with inconsistent motility is not consistent but eradication of *H. pylori* improves the symptoms of functional dyspepsia.²

H.pylori is a pathogen in the human stomach that is associated with the development of pathological conditions in the stomach such as gastritis, peptic ulcer, atrophy, metaplasia, dysplasia and gastric cancer.^{7,8}*H. pylori* is the main etiology of chronic gastritis.⁹This is consistent with the results of the study by Haziri et al, where the prevalence of gastritis with *H.pylori* positive was 66%.¹⁰In addition, based on data obtained by Lina et al, *H.pylori* expression was found in chronic gastritis as much as 84.6%. Another study revealed that patients with chronic gastritis found 70% with positive *H. pylori*. So that it can be said that *H.pylori* plays a role in the occurrence of chronic gastritis.¹¹

Hypoxic Inducible Factor (HIF) is a transcription factor involved in adaptation to low oxygen conditions. HIF also prolongs the life of neutrophils by inhibiting the apoptotic pathway. HIF has a role in inflammatory signals.

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HIF-1 is induced by phagocytes by a number of bacteria even in low oxygen conditions. ⁶HIF-1 α is not only regulated by hypoxic conditions, but also in response to various pressures, growth factors and coagulation, hormones or cytokines under normoxic conditions. This HIF-1 α stimulus in normoxic conditions often involves a different regulated protein kinase pathway for signal transduction which shows the important role of various kinases in the regulation of HIF-1 α . ¹²

H.pylori will cause an increase in HIF-1 α with a variety of pathways both directly and indirectly, where HIF-1 α will remain stable in macrophages in the stomach of patients with *H.pylori* infection. ^{7,13} Reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced as a result of neutrophil infiltration in response to *H.pylori* cause stable HIF-1 α resulting in increased proliferation, apoptosis and inflammation that end in epithelial cell injury. ¹⁴ Some studies mention the role of cytokines in inducing ROS, where ROS will directly activate from HIF so that there is an increase in HIF levels. ^{15,16,17}

Seeing the role of *H.pylori* in activators and degradation inhibitors of HIF-1 α under normoxic conditions, this study aims to determine the ratio of HIF1- α levels in gastritis patients with positive and negative *H.pylori* with blood samples from HIF1- α not from the gastric mucosa.

Material methods

Design of the study

This study was cross sectional design and was conducted in Endoscopic unit Adam Malik Hospital (RSHAM), Medan, North Sumatera, Indonesia from Maret-September 2019.

Subjects of the study

The sample of this study was patients with dyspepsia who came to RSHAM at the time of the sampling, who were more than 17 years and diagnosed with gastritis. The exclusion criteria of the study subjects were not cooperative patient, pregnant, has a systemic disease and malignancy, get *H.pylori* eradication therapy in the last 6 months, take antibiotics in the last 2 weeks and take PPI drugs in the last 2 weeks.

Diagnosis of dyspepsia is established based on the criteria of Rome III, accordance with the 2014 Dyspepsia Consensus. Gastritis is diagnosed histopathologically based on examination of tissue taken during a gastroscopy.

H.pylori measurement

All endoscopic examinations were using a skoop (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan). The endoscopic procedure is performed by an endoscopic who is experienced and the same in each study sample. Before endoscopy is carried out, patients are fasted for 8-12 hours. The *H. pylori* examination method is performed with RUT / CLO which is a fast urease test. This examination uses samples from tissue biopsy obtained during endoscopy. The results are read in the first 24 hours, where the reading time depends on bacterial concentration and temperature. The majority of positive changes occur in 120-180 minutes. If the results are negative, readings are waited for up to 24 hours. If after 24 hours, the results cannot be used. Yellow shows a negative result, while the results are positive if the color changes from yellow to red, magenta, pink or orange within 24 hours of incubation period at room temperature.

HIF-1 α measurement

This marker was examined by the ELISA sandwich method using Invitrogen HIF-1 Alpha Elisa Kit. This kit measures HIF-1 α levels in serum, plasma and cell culture lysate, and in this study we used the HIF-1 α levels in serum. The results obtained are nominal with units of pg / ml. This tool is capable of detecting HIF-1 α levels in a range between 81.9-20,000 pg/ ml.

Ethical clearance

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This study obtained ethical clearance from the Health Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Sumatera Utara.

Statistical analysis

The normality of the data was determined using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Statistical analysis in this study using the Mann Whitney test. A p-value of 0,05 was considered significant.

Result

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the study subjects, where this study was followed by 80 patients who had met the inclusion criteria where there were 49 male (61.3%) and female 31 (38.8%). The mean BMI found was 23.36 kg / m². Batak is the most ethnic group of research subjects with 46 people (57.5%), while the rest are Javanese 28 people (35.0%) and Aceh 6 people (7.5%).

Tabel 1. Characteristics of Research Subjects

Characteristic	n = 80
Sex, n (%)	
Male	49 (61.2)
Female	31 (38.8)
BMI, mean, kg/m²	23.36
Ethnic	
Batak	48 (57.5)
Javanese	28 (35.0)
Aceh	6 (7.5)
Occupation, n (%)	
Employee	35 (43.8)
Housewife	18 (22.5)
Enterpriser	22 (27.5)
Government employees	5 (6.3)
Education, n (%)	
Elementary school	3 (3.8)
Junior high school	20 (25.0)
Senior high school	41 (51.3)
University	16 (20.0)

The majority of occupation in the research subjects were employees, 35 people (43.8%), then 22 enterpriser (27.5%), 18 housewife (22.5%) and 5 government employees (6.3%). The most education in the research subjects were senior high school with a total of 41 people (51.3%), the next sequence was junior high school 20 people (25.0%), university 16 people (20.0%) and elementary school 3 people (3.8%).

Table 2 displays the levels of HIF-1 α in the positive and negative *H.pylori*. HIF-1 α levels were found in the range of 45-119 in the positive *H.pylori* (median: 89.50) and 34-86 in the negative *H.pylori* (median: 54.00).

Tabel 2. Comparison HIF-1 α in the Positive and Negative H.pylori

Characteristic	<i>H.pylori</i> Positive (n=28)	<i>H.pylori</i> Negative (n=52)	P
HIF-1α, median (min- max)	89.50 (45- 119)	54.00 (34-86)	<0.001*

* Statistically significant (p<0.05)

From the results of bivariate analysis using the Mann-Whitney test, a comparison of HIF-1 α levels was found to be significantly higher in the positive *H.pylori* than the negative *H.pylori* (p < 0.001).

Discussion

From the results of the study found that male patients suffer more gastritis than women, namely 49 people (61.2%) and 31 people (38.8%). As research reports from previous studies where in 273 gastritis patients studied, found gastritis patients with *H. pylori* positive 174 male (73.42%) and 63 female (26.58%).¹⁸

The most common tribes based on the results of this study are the Batak, followed by Java and Aceh with a total of 46 people (57.5%), 28 people (35%) and 6 people (7.5%). The same thing was also found in previous studies conducted by Fiblia et al at H. Adam Malik General Hospital in 2014, obtained from 80 total patients endoscoped with gastritis results, the majority of which were Batak ethnicity of 60.6%.¹⁹

Negative *H. pylori* was more common than positive *H. pylori* in the sample of gastritis patients in this study, namely 28 people (46.67%) *H. pylori* positive and 52 people (53.33%) *H. pylori* negative. This is in line with the results of Agbor et al's study which reported that from 500 samples of patients with gastritis there were more samples with *H. pylori* negative than positive, namely 263 people (52.6%) with *H. pylori* negative and 237 people (47.4%) with *H. pylori* positive.¹⁸

HIF-1 α is one of the main pathways that play a role and has a relationship with the inflammatory process, where inflammation is a non-specific complex which is a coordinated response of injured tissue. Likewise with gastritis which is also an inflammatory condition that occurs in the lining of the stomach with one of the causes that is often found is the involvement of *H. pylori*. *H. pylori* can cause persistent and local inflammation through the induction of oxidative stress and activation of ROS.^{20,21} Chronic, continuous *H. pylori* infection will increase from the induction of a factor induced by hypoxic conditions, namely HIF-1 α . This theory is in accordance with the results of this study which found levels of HIF-1 α in patients with *H. pylori* positive gastritis significantly higher than *H. pylori* negative. In addition, there are results of previous studies that explain that activation of *H. pylori* from the PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathway in gastric cells will increase the expression of HIF-1 α .²²

Another theory supporting the results of this study is that oxygen concentration is not the only factor that regulates HIF-1 α , cytokines released during inflammatory conditions also have a significant regulatory role in the induction of HIF-1 α .²³ This is due to there are 2 pathways of HIF-1 α regulation which are oxygen dependent and inflammatory stimuli. Proinflammatory cytokines, growth factors and bacterial products can increase HIF-1 α transcription through NF- κ B stimulation.²¹

Limitations of this study are the relatively small number of samples and the exclusion of confounding factors in the form of other etiologies of gastritis besides *H. pylori*.

Conclusion

In summary, HIF1- α levels are higher in patients with positive *H. pylori* gastritis than negative. Further research needs to be done by increasing the number of research samples so that more accurate results can be obtained and is expected to determine the ideal cut-off for HIF-1 α levels in gastritis patients so that HIF-1 α can be used as a parameter in predicting *H. pylori* infection status and inflammatory conditions.

Disclosure

All authors have contributed to the manuscript equally. None of the authors have direct or financial conflicts of interest with this paper and material contained herein.

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